

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Generalised neo-pseudo projective recurrent Finsler space

Indiwar Singh Chauhan^{1*}, T S Chauhan², Mohammad Gauhar³

¹ Assistant Professor, Deptt. of Mathematics, Bareilly College, Bareilly (U.P.), India. Tel.: 09219269009

² Associate Professor, Deptt. of Mathematics, Bareilly College, Bareilly (U.P.), India

³ Research Scholar, IFTM University, Moradabad (U.P.), India

Received: 13.08.2020

Accepted: 18.01.2021

Published: 01.02.2021

Citation: Chauhan IS, Chauhan TS, Gauhar M (2021) Generalised neo-pseudo projective recurrent Finsler space. Indian Journal of Science and Technology 14(4): 289-296. <https://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/v14i4.1410>

* **Corresponding author.**

Tel: 09219269009
indiwarsingh.chauhan@gmail.com

Funding: None

Competing Interests: None

Copyright: © 2021 Chauhan et al. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Published By Indian Society for Education and Environment ([iSee](#))

ISSN

Print: 0974-6846

Electronic: 0974-5645

Abstract

Objectives: The purpose of this paper is to obtain several results in the field of generalised neo-pseudo projective recurrent Finsler space. **Methods:** A generalization technique is employed to solve the resulting problem. We provide its application in the study of space-time. **Findings:** In section 1, we have defined and studied some of the basic and useful results for later work. Section 2 deals for the neo-pseudo projective recurrent curvature tensor. The notion of neo-pseudo projective recurrent space of second order has been delineated in the section 3. In the section 4 we have studied the generalised neo-pseudo projective recurrent space and established several new results. **Novelty/Conclusion:** In this paper we have studied some recurrent properties of neo-pseudo projective curvature tensor in a Finsler space. We have obtained several new results which are as follows:

- If the space F^n admits a neo-pseudo projective curvature tensor $Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha$ then $Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha$ is skew-symmetric with regard to last two indices.
- If the neo-pseudo projective deviation tensor Q_β^α and pseudo deviation tensor field T_β^α coincides to each other for $q = 1$ then space is W-flat.
- If F^n admits the projectively flat Q-recurrent space then the relation $\nabla_\varepsilon Q_{\beta\gamma}^\alpha + \nabla_\beta Q_{\gamma\varepsilon}^\alpha + \nabla_\gamma Q_{\varepsilon\beta}^\alpha = 0$ holds good.
- If a Finsler space F^n admits projectively flat Q-birecurrent space then the relation $K_{\varepsilon\rho} Q_{\beta\gamma}^\alpha + K_{\beta\rho} Q_{\gamma\varepsilon}^\alpha + K_{\gamma\rho} Q_{\varepsilon\beta}^\alpha = 0$ holds good.
- If the space is Q-birecurrent then the generalised Q-recurrent space is Q-symmetric.
- For the projective flat generalised Q-recurrent space the relation $\nabla_\rho \nabla_\varepsilon Q_{\gamma\delta}^\alpha + \nabla_\rho \nabla_\gamma Q_{\delta\varepsilon}^\alpha + \nabla_\rho \nabla_\delta Q_{\varepsilon\gamma}^\alpha = 0$ holds good.

AMS Subject Classification: 58B20, 53C20, 53C60.

Keywords: Neo-pseudo; recurrent; projective; curvature tensor; bisymmetric; flat

1 Introduction

Let F^n be an n-dimensional Finsler space with a positive definite metric $g_{\alpha\beta}$, which admit a projective deviation tensor field W_{β}^{α} and pseudo deviation tensor field T_{β}^{α} satisfying

$$Q_{\beta}^{\alpha} = p W_{\beta}^{\alpha} + q T_{\beta}^{\alpha} \tag{1.1}$$

where in p and q are scalars which are positively homogenous of degree zero in \dot{x}^{α} .

Prof. U.P. Singh and Prof. A.K. Singh while developing the theory of neo-pseudo projective curvature tensor, obtain two kinds of curvature tensor $Q_{\beta\gamma}^{\alpha}$ and $Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^{\alpha}$ ⁽¹⁾. With a view to defining the projective deviation tensor field and pseudo deviation tensor field, he constructed the quantities $Q_{\beta}^{\alpha}(x, \dot{x})$ which behave like neo-pseudo projective deviation tensor.

With the help of tensor $Q_{\beta}^{\alpha}(x, \dot{x})$ the absolute differential of concerning vector referred to the scalar function $Q(x, \dot{x})$ is defined as follows⁽¹⁻³⁾:

$$Q_{\beta\gamma}^{\alpha} = \frac{1}{3}(\dot{\partial}_{\beta} Q_{\gamma}^{\alpha} - \dot{\partial}_{\gamma} Q_{\beta}^{\alpha}) \tag{1.2}$$

and

$$Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^{\alpha} = \dot{\partial}_{\beta} Q_{\gamma\delta}^{\alpha} \tag{1.3}$$

It is easy to verify that the neo-pseudo projective curvature tensor satisfies the following relations^(1,4):

$$Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^{\alpha} + Q_{\gamma\delta\beta}^{\alpha} + Q_{\delta\beta\gamma}^{\alpha} = 0 \tag{1.4}$$

$$Q_{\beta\gamma}^{\alpha} \dot{x}^{\beta} = Q_{\gamma}^{\alpha} \tag{1.5}$$

and

$$Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^{\alpha} \dot{x}^{\beta} = Q_{\gamma\delta}^{\alpha} \tag{1.6}$$

Moreover, these curvature tensor also satisfy the following identities

$$Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^{\alpha} \dot{x}^{\beta} \dot{x}^{\gamma} = Q_{\delta}^{\alpha} \tag{1.7}$$

and

$$Q_{\beta}^{\alpha} \dot{x}^{\beta} = 0 \tag{1.8}$$

As it is well known, in the Finsler space a scalar function $Q(x, \dot{x})$ is given by

$$Q_{\alpha}^{\alpha} = (n - 1)qT \tag{1.9}$$

Let us consider a curvature tensor W_{β}^{α} in Finsler space, is termed as projective curvature tensor in the Finsler space and is defined as follows^(2,5,6):

$$W_{\beta}^{\alpha} = H_{\beta}^{\alpha} + T_{\beta}^{\alpha} \tag{1.10}$$

Wherein H_{β}^{α} is positively homogeneous of degree one in \dot{x}^{α} .

In analogy with the relation (1.1) the projective curvature tensors $W_{\beta\gamma}^{\alpha}$ and $W_{\beta\gamma\delta}^{\alpha}$ in the Finsler space with the condition p = q = 1 may be defined as follows^(2,7):

$$W_{\beta}^{\alpha} = H_{\beta}^{\alpha} + Q_{\beta}^{\alpha} \tag{1.11}$$

$$W_{\beta\gamma}^{\alpha} = H_{\beta\gamma}^{\alpha} + Q_{\beta\gamma}^{\alpha} \tag{1.12}$$

and

$$W_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha = H_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha + Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha \tag{1.13}$$

In view of above discussions, we have the following theorems:

Theorem 1.1:

For the neo-pseudo projective curvature tensor the relation

$$Q_{\beta\gamma}^\alpha = -Q_{\gamma\beta}^\alpha \tag{1.14}$$

holds good.

Proof:

Interchanging β and γ in equation (1.2) and adding this with new equation, we get the desired result.

Theorem 1.2:

If the space F^n admits a neo-pseudo projective curvature tensor $Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha$ then $Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha$ is skew-symmetric with regard to last two indices.

Proof:

Interchanging γ and δ in equation (1.3) and adding the new equation to the equation (1.3), we obtain

$$Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha + Q_{\beta\delta\gamma}^\alpha = \dot{\partial}_\beta Q_{\gamma\delta}^\alpha + \dot{\partial}_\beta Q_{\delta\gamma}^\alpha \tag{1.15}$$

From equations (1.14) and (1.15), we get

$$Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha = -Q_{\beta\delta\gamma}^\alpha \tag{1.16}$$

Theorem 1.3:

If the neo-pseudo projective deviation tensor Q_β^α coincides with geodesic deviation tensor field H_β^α in the Finsler space F^n then projective deviation tensor field W_β^α and the neo-pseudo projective deviation tensor Q_β^α are identically equal to each other.

Proof:

If the neo-pseudo projective deviation tensor Q_β^α coincides with geodesic deviation tensor field H_β^α . Consequently, from equation (1.11) follows

$$W_\beta^\alpha = Q_\beta^\alpha \tag{1.17}$$

Hence projective deviation tensor field W_β^α and the neo-pseudo projective deviation tensor Q_β^α are identically equal to each other.

Theorem 1.4:

If the neo-pseudo projective deviation tensor Q_β^α and pseudo deviation tensor field T_β^α coincides to each other for $q = 1$ then Finsler space admits the condition $W_\beta^\alpha = 0$ i.e. W-flat.

Proof:

Insetting $q = 1$ in equation (1.1), we obtain

$$Q_\beta^\alpha = p W_\beta^\alpha + T_\beta^\alpha \tag{1.18}$$

If the neo-pseudo projective deviation tensor Q_β^α and pseudo deviation tensor field T_β^α coincides to each other then from equation (1.18) we observe that

$$W_\beta^\alpha = 0 \tag{1.19}$$

This manifests that the space is W-flat.

Theorem 1.5:

If the neo-pseudo projective deviation tensor Q_β^α and projective deviation tensor field W_β^α coincides to each other then the geodesic deviation tensor field H_β^α vanish identically i.e. H-flat.

Proof:

If the neo-pseudo projective deviation tensor Q_{β}^{α} and projective deviation tensor field W_{β}^{α} coincides to each other then from equation (1.11) follows the result

$$H_{\beta}^{\alpha} = 0 \tag{1.20}$$

Consequently, the space is H-flat.

Theorem 1.6:

If the projective deviation tensor field W_{β}^{α} and geodesic deviation tensor field H_{β}^{α} coincides to each other then the neo-pseudo projective deviation tensor Q_{β}^{α} vanish identically i.e. Q-flat.

Proof:

If the projective deviation tensor field W_{β}^{α} and geodesic deviation tensor field H_{β}^{α} coincides to each other. Consequently, from equation (1.11) follows

$$Q_{\beta}^{\alpha} = 0 \tag{1.21}$$

Therefore the space is Q-flat.

2 Recurrent neo-pseudo projective curvature tensor in Finsler space

In view of the investigation of Prof. U.P. Singh and Prof. A.K. Singh⁽¹⁾ we observe that if the neo-pseudo projective deviation tensor Q_{β}^{α} is necessarily recurrent then projective deviation tensor and pseudo deviation tensor are proportional to each other.

As a consequence of this follows the result

$$W_{\beta}^{\alpha} = t T_{\beta}^{\alpha} \tag{2.1}$$

wherein t is a scalar.

As a consequence of equations (1.1) and (2.1), we obtain

$$Q_{\beta}^{\alpha} = s T_{\beta}^{\alpha} \tag{2.2}$$

wherein $s = pt + q$ is any scalar and positively homogeneous of degree zero in x^{α} .

Definition 2.1:

A Finsler space whose curvature tensor is recurrent is called Q-recurrent Finsler space.

In view of the definition it follows that for a recurrent space, we have

$$\nabla_{\epsilon} Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^{\alpha} = R_{\epsilon} Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^{\alpha} \tag{2.3}$$

wherein R_{ϵ} is a non-zero vector termed as the recurrent vector field.

Definition 2.2:

An n-dimensional Finsler space F^n is called Q-symmetric when the covariant derivative of curvature tensor is everywhere zero i.e.

$$\nabla_{\epsilon} Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^{\alpha} = 0 \tag{2.4}$$

Definition 2.3:

A Finsler space F^n is said to be Q-flat when its curvature tensor vanishes identically.

As a consequence of this definition follows the result:

$$Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^{\alpha} = 0 \tag{2.5}$$

Contracting (2.3) with x^{β} and use of equation (1.6), we obtain

$$\nabla_{\epsilon} Q_{\gamma\delta}^{\alpha} = R_{\epsilon} Q_{\gamma\delta}^{\alpha} \tag{2.6}$$

Again contracting (2.6) with x^{γ} and making use of equation (1.5), we get

$$\nabla_{\epsilon} Q_{\delta}^{\alpha} = R_{\epsilon} Q_{\delta}^{\alpha} \tag{2.7}$$

Thus, we have now the following theorem:

Theorem 2.1:

For the recurrence vector space R_ϵ in the Finsler space F^n there exists the relation $(\nabla_\rho \nabla_\epsilon - \nabla_\epsilon \nabla_\rho)(\log T) = (\nabla_\rho R_\epsilon - \nabla_\epsilon R_\rho)$.

Proof:

Differentiating (2.3) covariantly with regard to x^ρ , we get

$$\nabla_\rho \nabla_\epsilon Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha = (\nabla_\rho R_\epsilon + R_\epsilon R_\rho) Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha \tag{2.8}$$

Interchanging ϵ and δ in equation (2.8) and subtracting the new equation from equation (2.8), we obtain

$$\nabla_\rho \nabla_\epsilon Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha - \nabla_\epsilon \nabla_\rho Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha = (\nabla_\rho R_\epsilon - \nabla_\epsilon R_\rho) Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha \tag{2.9}$$

Contracting (2.9) with $x^\beta x^\gamma$ and use of equation (1.7), we get

$$\nabla_\rho \nabla_\epsilon Q_\delta^\alpha - \nabla_\epsilon \nabla_\rho Q_\delta^\alpha = (\nabla_\rho R_\epsilon - \nabla_\epsilon R_\rho) Q_\delta^\alpha \tag{2.10}$$

Contracting α and δ in equation (2.10) and use of equation (1.9), we obtain

$$(\nabla_\rho \nabla_\epsilon - \nabla_\epsilon \nabla_\rho)(\log T) = (\nabla_\rho R_\epsilon - \nabla_\epsilon R_\rho) \tag{2.11}$$

Definition 2.4:

If the neo-pseudo projective curvature tensor $Q_{\beta\gamma}^\alpha$ in the Finsler space F^n satisfies the relation

$$\nabla_\epsilon Q_{\beta\gamma}^\alpha = R_\epsilon Q_{\beta\gamma}^\alpha \tag{2.12}$$

then F^n is termed as Q-recurrent with recurrence vector field R_ϵ .

Consequently, we have a theorem:

Theorem 2.2:

If F^n admits the projectively flat Q-recurrent space then the relation $\nabla_\epsilon Q_{\beta\gamma}^\alpha + \nabla_\beta Q_{\gamma\epsilon}^\alpha + \nabla_\gamma Q_{\epsilon\beta}^\alpha = 0$ holds good.

Proof:

If the space is projectively flat then from equation (1.12), we have

$$H_{\beta\gamma}^\alpha + Q_{\beta\gamma}^\alpha = 0 \tag{2.13}$$

Differentiating (2.13) covariantly with respect to x^ϵ , we get

$$\nabla_\epsilon H_{\beta\gamma}^\alpha + \nabla_\epsilon Q_{\beta\gamma}^\alpha = 0 \tag{2.14}$$

Taking the cyclic permutation in β, γ, ϵ and adding, we have

$$\left(\nabla_\epsilon H_{\beta\gamma}^\alpha + \nabla_\beta H_{\gamma\epsilon}^\alpha + \nabla_\gamma H_{\epsilon\beta}^\alpha \right) + \left(\nabla_\epsilon Q_{\beta\gamma}^\alpha + \nabla_\beta Q_{\gamma\epsilon}^\alpha + \nabla_\gamma Q_{\epsilon\beta}^\alpha \right) = 0 \tag{2.15}$$

The first part of equation (2.15) vanishes due to commutation formula ⁽⁸⁾, equation (6.13), p.128), hence we obtain

$$\nabla_\epsilon Q_{\beta\gamma}^\alpha + \nabla_\beta Q_{\gamma\epsilon}^\alpha + \nabla_\gamma Q_{\epsilon\beta}^\alpha = 0 \tag{2.16}$$

3 Neo-Pseudo Projective Recurrent Space:

Definition 3.1:

Neo-pseudo projective curvature tensor $Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha$ of a Finsler space satisfies the relation

$$\nabla_\rho \nabla_\epsilon Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha = K_{\epsilon\rho} Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha \tag{3.1}$$

wherein $K_{\epsilon\rho}$ is non-zero recurrent tensor, then it is called neo-pseudo projective recurrent space of second order or briefly a Q-birecurrent space^(3,4).

Definition 3.2:

If the covariant derivative of neo-pseudo projective curvature tensor $Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha$ vanishes identically then the space is termed as Q-bisymmetric.

As a consequence of above definition follows the result

$$\nabla_\rho \nabla_\epsilon Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha = 0 \tag{3.2}$$

In this regard we shall now establish the following theorem:

Theorem 3.1:

The necessary and sufficient condition for Finsler space to be Q-bisymmetric space is that the neo-pseudo projective tensor vanishes identically.

Proof:

Since neo-pseudo projective tensor vanishes i.e. $Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha = 0$. Consequently from equation (3.1) it follows that $\nabla_\rho \nabla_\epsilon Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha = 0$. This manifests that the space to be Q-bisymmetric.

Conversely, if the space to be Q-bisymmetric then the converse of theorem is immediately proof.

Remark 3.1:

It is noteworthy that every Q-recurrent is necessarily Q-birecurrent.

Theorem 3.2:

In a Finsler space F^n , the recurrent tensor field $K_{\epsilon\rho}$ is not symmetric in general.

Proof:

Contracting α and δ in equation (3.1) yields

$$\nabla_\rho \nabla_\epsilon Q_{\beta\gamma} = K_{\epsilon\rho} Q_{\beta\gamma} \tag{3.3}$$

Interchanging ϵ and ρ in equation (3.3) and subtracting the new equation from equation (3.3), we obtain

$$\nabla_\rho \nabla_\epsilon Q_{\beta\gamma} - \nabla_\epsilon \nabla_\rho Q_{\beta\gamma} = (K_{\epsilon\rho} - K_{\rho\epsilon}) Q_{\beta\gamma} \tag{3.4}$$

Contracting (3.4) with $\dot{x}^\beta \dot{x}^\gamma$ and use of equation (1.7), we get

$$\nabla_\rho \nabla_\epsilon Q - \nabla_\epsilon \nabla_\rho Q = (K_{\epsilon\rho} - K_{\rho\epsilon}) Q \tag{3.5}$$

Using commutation formula ⁽⁵⁾, equation (6.10), p.126) and equation (2.2), we obtain

$$(K_{\epsilon\rho} - K_{\rho\epsilon}) Q = (\partial_\sigma Q) H_{\rho\epsilon}^\sigma \tag{3.6}$$

From equations (1.9) and (3.6), consequently, follows

$$K_{\epsilon\rho} - K_{\rho\epsilon} = \partial_\sigma (\log T) H_{\rho\epsilon}^\sigma \tag{3.7}$$

Yields the result

$$K_{\epsilon\rho} \neq K_{\rho\epsilon} \tag{3.8}$$

Theorem 3.3:

If a Finsler space F^n admits projectively flat Q-birecurrent space then the relation $K_{\epsilon\rho} Q_{\beta\gamma}^\alpha + K_{\beta\rho} Q_{\gamma\epsilon}^\alpha + K_{\gamma\rho} Q_{\epsilon\beta}^\alpha = 0$ holds good.

Proof:

Differentiating equation (2.16) covariantly with respect to x^ρ , we get

$$\nabla_\rho \nabla_\epsilon Q_{\beta\gamma}^\alpha + \nabla_\rho \nabla_\beta Q_{\gamma\epsilon}^\alpha + \nabla_\rho \nabla_\gamma Q_{\epsilon\beta}^\alpha = 0 \tag{3.9}$$

Since the space is Q-birecurrent then equation (3.2) assumes the form

$$K_{\epsilon\rho} Q_{\beta\gamma}^\alpha + K_{\beta\rho} Q_{\gamma\epsilon}^\alpha + K_{\gamma\rho} Q_{\epsilon\beta}^\alpha = 0 \tag{3.10}$$

4 Generalised Neo-Pseudo Projective Recurrent Space:

Let us consider the relation

$$\nabla_\rho \nabla_\epsilon Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha = R_\rho \nabla_\epsilon Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha + K_{\epsilon\rho} Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha \tag{4.1}$$

wherein R_ρ and $K_{\epsilon\rho}$ are recurrence vector and recurrence tensor fields respectively.

Definition 4.1:

The neo-pseudo projective curvature tensor $Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha$ of Finsler space F^n satisfying the condition (4.1) is called generalised neo-pseudo projective recurrent curvature tensor^(3,4).

Definition 4.2:

Finsler space F^n equipped with the generalised neo-pseudo projective recurrent curvature tensor $Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha$ is called generalised neo-pseudo projective recurrent Finsler space^(3,9).

In this regard, we have the following theorems:

Theorem 4.1:

The necessary and sufficient condition for Finsler space F^n to be Q-symmetric is that the space has to be Q-birecurrent.

Proof:

If the space is to be Q-symmetric i.e. $\nabla_\epsilon Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha = 0$,

Consequently, from equation (4.1) follows

$$\nabla_\rho \nabla_\epsilon Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha = K_{\epsilon\rho} Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha \tag{4.2}$$

which is the condition of Q-birecurrent.

Conversely, let us assume that the space be Q-birecurrent, follows the condition (4.2). Inserting equation (4.2) into equation (4.1), we obtain $\nabla_\epsilon Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha = 0$. Hence the space is Q-symmetric.

Theorem 4.2:

If the space F^n is Q-symmetric and Q-flat then its generalised neo-pseudo projective recurrent space vanishes identically.

Proof:

If the space be Q-symmetric i.e. $\nabla_\epsilon Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha = 0$ and Q-flat i.e. $Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha = 0$. Consequently, from equation (4.1) follows $\nabla_\rho \nabla_\epsilon Q_{\beta\gamma\delta}^\alpha = 0$. This establishes the validity of the theorem.

Remark 4.1:

It is noteworthy that if F^n to be Q-symmetric and Q-flat follows that the generalised neo-pseudo projective recurrent space necessarily vanishes. Consequently, the space is simply generalised Q-symmetric one.

Theorem 4.3:

If space F^n admits Q-symmetric and Q-flat then the space is a generalised Q-symmetric one.

Proof:

It follows immediately from theorem 4.2.

Theorem 4.4:

In Finsler space F^n , if the space is Q-birecurrent then the generalised Q-recurrent space is Q-symmetric.

Proof:

It is obvious from equations (2.4), (3.1) and (4.1).

Theorem 4.5:

For the recurrence vector R_ρ the relation

$$R_\rho \nabla_\epsilon T - R_\epsilon \nabla_\rho T = 0 \tag{4.3}$$

holds good.

Proof:

Contracting (4.1) by α and δ , we obtain

$$\nabla_\rho \nabla_\epsilon Q_{\beta\gamma} = R_\rho \nabla_\epsilon Q_{\beta\gamma} + K_{\epsilon\rho} Q_{\beta\gamma} \tag{4.4}$$

Interchanging ϵ and ρ in equation (4.4) and subtracting the new equation from equation (4.4), we get

$$\nabla_\rho \nabla_\epsilon Q_{\beta\gamma} - \nabla_\epsilon \nabla_\rho Q_{\beta\gamma} = R_\rho \nabla_\epsilon Q_{\beta\gamma} - R_\epsilon \nabla_\rho Q_{\beta\gamma} + (K_{\epsilon\rho} - K_{\rho\epsilon}) Q_{\beta\gamma} \tag{4.5}$$

Contracting (4.5) with $x^\beta x^\gamma$ and use of equation (1.7), we get

$$\nabla_\rho \nabla_\varepsilon Q - \nabla_\varepsilon \nabla_\rho Q = R_\rho \nabla_\varepsilon Q - R_\varepsilon \nabla_\rho Q + (K_{\varepsilon\rho} - K_{\rho\varepsilon})Q \tag{4.6}$$

By virtue of equations (3.5) and (4.6), we get

$$R_\rho \nabla_\varepsilon Q - R_\varepsilon \nabla_\rho Q = 0 \tag{4.7}$$

Inserting equation (1.9) in equation (4.7), we get the desired result.

Theorem 4.6:

For the projective flat generalised Q-recurrent space the relation $\nabla_\rho \nabla_\varepsilon Q_{\gamma\delta}^\alpha + \nabla_\rho \nabla_\gamma Q_{\delta\varepsilon}^\alpha + \nabla_\rho \nabla_\delta Q_{\varepsilon\gamma}^\alpha = 0$ holds good.

Proof:

Contracting (4.1) with x^β , we obtain

$$\nabla_\rho \nabla_\varepsilon Q_{\gamma\delta}^\alpha = R_\rho \nabla_\varepsilon Q_{\gamma\delta}^\alpha + K_{\varepsilon\rho} Q_{\gamma\delta}^\alpha \tag{4.8}$$

Taking the cyclic permutation in $\varepsilon, \gamma, \delta$ and on making use of equations (2.16) and (3.10), we observe that

$$\nabla_\rho \nabla_\varepsilon Q_{\gamma\delta}^\alpha + \nabla_\rho \nabla_\gamma Q_{\delta\varepsilon}^\alpha + \nabla_\rho \nabla_\delta Q_{\varepsilon\gamma}^\alpha = 0 \tag{4.9}$$

References

- 1) Singh UP, Singh AK. On neo-pseudo projective tensor fields. *Indian J Pure Appl Math.* 1979;10(10):1196–1201.
- 2) Dubey RSD, Singh H. Finsler spaces with recurrent pseudocurvatures tensor. *Proceedings Mathematical Sciences.* 1979;88(4):363–367. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1007/bf02842482>.
- 3) Singh UP, Singh AK. Finsler spaces admitting recurrent neo-pseudo projective tensor fields. *Indian J Pure Appl Math.* 1981;12(10):1201–1207. Available from: https://insa.nic.in/writereaddata/UploadedFiles/IJPAM/20005a82_1201.pdf.
- 4) Abdallah AA, Navlekar AA, Ghadle KP. On Study Generalized BP – Recurrent Finsler Space. *International Journal of Mathematics Trends and Technology.* 2019;65(4):74–79. Available from: <https://dx.doi.org/10.14445/22315373/ijmtt-v65i4p514>.
- 5) Sinha BB. On projectively flat Finsler space and pseudo deviation tensor. *Prog Math.* 1971;5:88–92.
- 6) Srivastava SK, Mishra AK, P. Recurrent Finsler spaces theorem in projective recurrent spaces of third order. *International Journal of Science, Environment and Technology.* 2016;5(1):185–194. Available from: <http://www.ijset.net/journal/856.pdf>.
- 7) Misra SB, Singh HC, Misra AK. On a neo-recurrent F_n^* . *Indian J Pure Appl Math.* 1985;16(3):232–242.
- 8) Rund H. *Differential Geometry of Finsler space.* Berlin. Springer-Verlag. 1959. Available from: <https://www.springer.com/gp/book/9783642516122>.
- 9) Gicheru JG, Ngari CG. Cyrus Gitonga Ngari: Decomposition of Riemannian curvature tensor field and its properties. *Journal of advances in mathematics and computer science.* 2019;30(1):1–15. Available from: <https://www.journaljamcs.com/index.php/JAMCS/article/view/28855>.